

NON-TEACHING RESPONSIBILITIES VIS-a-VIS PEDAGOGICAL DELIVERY PRIORITIES

CRISTINE JOY B. MANON-OG

Abstract. The study assessed the relationship between non-teaching responsibilities and teachers' pedagogical delivery priorities in Maco North District, Davao de Oro Schools Division. This used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the 120 randomly selected teacher-respondents. The treatments used were mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and simple linear regression analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of doing non-teaching responsibilities in terms of administrative duties; and school committee participation are oftentimes manifested; student support services and professional development are sometimes manifested; parent and community engagement is rarely manifested, thus, moderately extensive; learning objectives is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive; while, pedagogical deliveries in terms of use of technology, assessment and feedback, and differentiation are oftentimes manifested; while, learning objectives is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between non-teaching responsibilities and pedagogical delivery priorities. All domains of non-teaching responsibilities regarding administrative duties, professional development, student support service, parent and community engagement, and school committee participation suggest significantly influenced the pedagogical delivery priorities of teachers. Future research may investigate the scalability of successful practices to different educational contexts.

KEY WORDS

1. Non-teaching responsibilities.
2. pedagogical delivery priorities.
3. descriptive-correlational research .

1. Introduction

The impact of non-teaching responsibilities on teachers' pedagogical delivery priorities is an ongoing concern marked by several prominent trends. One significant trend is the increasing administrative burden placed on educators. Across countries, teachers are grappling with a growing array of administrative tasks, such as data collection, reporting, and compliance with standardized testing. These tasks can consume a substantial amount of teachers' time and energy, often diverting their focus from classroom instruction and shaping their pedagogical priorities—moreover, the range of non-teaching roles that teachers assume is expanding. Beyond traditional classroom instruction, educators are being called upon to fulfill responsibilities related to student support, committee participation, and extracurricular activities. The diversity and volume of these roles vary from one educational context to another. There is

a growing recognition of the impact of non-teaching responsibilities on teacher well-being. Many teachers report experiencing elevated levels of stress and burnout due to the increased workload associated with these additional duties. This trend has led to discussions on the need for enhanced support mechanisms, professional development, and more manageable workloads to safeguard teachers' mental health and job satisfaction (Buchanan, 2020). International responses to these trends have been mixed. Some countries have implemented policies and initiatives to alleviate the impact of non-teaching responsibilities on educators. These measures may include workload reduction strategies, the allocation of additional support staff, and targeted professional development to equip teachers with the skills to manage their diverse roles more effectively. In parallel, a burgeoning body of research and advocacy efforts at the international level seeks to understand the complex interplay between non-teaching responsibilities and pedagogical delivery priorities. This research aims to provide evidence-based insights into the issue and inform policy discussions on balancing necessary administrative and support functions and the primary goal of effective classroom teaching (Li Li, 2022). Work intensification has increased the workload and complexity of work performed by principals and vice-principals. This case narrative accounts for work intensification in the secondary vice-principal role. The vice-principal role entails administrating various school operations and instructional leadership duties as the principal assigns. In particular, the role has evolved into "juggling" reactive and urgent school operations tasks with essential instructional leadership duties to improve student learning and achievement. The teaching notes address three tensions of the vice-principal role: developing and strengthening personal leadership resources, prioritizing school operations and instructional leadership duties, and striving for work-life bal-

ance (Lim, 2019).

In the Philippine educational system, the impact of non-teaching responsibilities on teachers' pedagogical delivery priorities has been a notable and evolving trend. One prominent trend is the increasing administrative burden placed on educators. Teachers are often tasked with extensive paperwork, including record-keeping, data collection, and compliance with standardized testing and reporting requirements. These administrative duties consume a significant portion of teachers' time and energy, potentially diverting their attention from classroom instruction and shaping their pedagogical priorities (Li Li, 2022). Another trend is the diversification of non-teaching roles that educators must fulfill. In addition to their core teaching responsibilities, teachers in the Philippines often take on roles related to student support, committee participation, and extracurricular activities. While valuable for students' holistic development, these roles can add to the complexity of teachers' workloads and influence their pedagogical choices. The impact of non-teaching responsibilities on teacher well-being is also a growing concern in the Philippine context. Many teachers report experiencing high levels of stress and burnout due to the demands of managing both teaching and non-teaching duties. This trend has prompted discussions on the need for improved support structures, professional development opportunities, and strategies to promote teacher well-being (Lim, 2019). In response to these trends, the Philippine educational system has tried to address the issue. Policy discussions and initiatives have been launched to alleviate the administrative load on teachers, enhance support mechanisms, and provide opportunities for skill development. Additionally, there is a growing recognition of the need to balance administrative and pedagogical responsibilities to ensure that teachers can continue to deliver practical and student-centered instruction (Li, et.al., 2022). In the

municipality of Maco, located in the province of Davao de Oro in the Philippines, several distinct trends influence the impact of non-teaching responsibilities on teachers' pedagogical delivery priorities. One notable trend is the increasing administrative demands placed on educators. Teachers in Maco are often tasked with extensive paperwork, record-keeping, and reporting requirements, which can consume a significant portion of their work hours. This administrative burden could divert their focus from classroom instruction and influence their pedagogical priorities. Another trend specific to Maco is the diversification of non-teaching roles that teachers are expected to assume. In addition to their primary teaching responsibilities, educators in the municipality are often involved in various extracurricular activities, committee work, and community engagement initiatives. While these roles contribute to the overall development of students and the community, they can add complexity to teachers' workloads and affect their ability to prioritize classroom teaching. Efforts are underway in Maco to address these trends. Local education authorities are engaged in policy discussions and initiatives to reduce administrative burdens on teachers, provide additional support, and foster a balance between non-teaching responsibilities and pedagogical priorities. As the educational landscape in Maco continues to evolve, finding ways to support teachers in managing their diverse roles while upholding the quality of pedagogical delivery remains a critical focus for the local educational community.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the processes and steps for conducting the study. Research methods are the systematic procedures and techniques researchers employ to gather, analyze, and interpret data to answer specific research questions or test hypotheses. These methods serve as the foundation for scientific inquiry, enabling researchers to design and conduct studies in a structured and rigorous manner. The choice of research method is influenced by the nature of the research objectives, the type of data needed, and the practical constraints of the study. In this context, the introduction provides an overview of the selected research method, highlighting its relevance, strengths, and limitations in the research endeavor. It is also worthy to note that the use of artificial intelligence of this article is limited only to proofreading, this statement is being divulged as an added ethical consideration in this new age of research writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. This design is a comprehensive approach to research methodology that combines several key elements to explore relationships and systematically predict outcomes. It typically involves observing and analyzing existing data or naturally occurring phenomena without intervention, manipulation, or control of variables (Creswell, 2014). In the "Non-Teaching Responsibilities on Teachers' Pedagogical Delivery Priorities" study, a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design is employed to investigate the relationship between teachers' non-teaching responsibilities and their pedagogical delivery priorities. This research design is particularly well-suited for exploring this topic as it allows researchers to observe and describe the existing conditions and associations among variables without manipulating them. The research aims to establish potential relationships or correlations between the extent of non-teaching responsibilities and the priority levels teachers

assign to their pedagogical duties through correlational analysis. In essence, this research design serves as a valuable tool for comprehensively exploring the intricate dynamics between non-teaching responsibilities and teachers' core instructional roles, shedding light on their interconnectedness and potential implications for educational practice and policy.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were elementary teachers in Maco North District, Davao de Oro Schools Division. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 120 teacher-respondents were taken randomly from each School. One randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platforms and face-to-face, considering the availability of Wi-Fi connections, and they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. These teacher-respondents were selected because they were assumed to have implemented various school learning programs, especially in non-related teaching activities. They are qualified because they were expected to have performed and contributed given that they have attended various activities aside from the school's curriculum delivery and implementation management. This is done through school faculty meetings and other group and committee meetings for the betterment of the school and the learners' awareness and educational stages given the new regular learning system during SY 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support of the

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of pedagogical delivery priorities, a 5-point Likert scale

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The preceding statements explain the data-gathering

school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This research study used the adapted instrument from reviewed literature and related studies. The researcher gathered and read reviews of related literature to develop concepts for the content that support the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question items, reducing threats to validity. As the authors argued, items were adapted from the reviewed literature. The survey questionnaire had two parts; one consisted of indicators of non-teaching-related responsibilities in administrative duties, student support services, parent and community engagement, and school committee participation. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the pedagogical delivery priorities regarding learning objectives, differentiation, assessment and feedback, and use of technology. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 confidence level. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.899, which means that the unidimensional reliability in terms of internal consistency is very good. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent doing non-teaching responsibilities. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

was used in this study, as presented below;

procedure steps that the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. Permission to conduct the study. The second week of Decem-

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The non-teaching responsibilities are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The non-teaching responsibilities are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The non-teaching responsibilities are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The non-teaching responsibilities are rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The non-teaching responsibilities are not manifested.

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The pedagogical delivery priorities of teachers are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The pedagogical delivery priorities of teachers are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The pedagogical delivery priorities of teachers are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The pedagogical delivery priorities of teachers are rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The pedagogical delivery priorities of teachers are not manifested.

ber 2023, the researcher started conceptualizing the thesis proposal's contents and objective. She then prepares documents such as letter requests in the conduct of the study. The research study adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004). From the last week of February up to the first week of March 2024, as soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao de Oro, through channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study among the Maco North District. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In May 2024, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents without internet access. Likewise, a prepared

hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with data gathering, which commenced on the third week of May 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of June 2024. For coaching and in terms of statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician to provide technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study sometime in the first week of June 2024 and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results on the second week of June 2024.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of doing non-teaching responsibilities, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of pedagogical delivery priorities. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between doing non-teaching responsibilities and pedagogical delivery pri-

orities. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of doing non-teaching responsibilities that significantly influence pedagogical delivery priorities (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations followed when results were yielded.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the responses from the data gathered in tabular and textual form. It includes discussions of the results based on an integration with reviews of the related studies. Given the hypothesis posed, this will be the basis for the decisions.

Table 1 summarizes the extent of non-teaching responsibilities. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: use of technology (3.52), assessment and feedback (3.50), and differentiation (3.42) are often manifested, while

learning objectives (3.02) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.36 denotes that the extent of implementation of the disciplinary challenges index is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Pedagogical Delivery Priorities

No	Pedagogical Delivery Priorities	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Learning Objectives	3.02	Moderately Extensive
2	Differentiation	3.42	Extensive
3	Use of Technology	3.52	Extensive
4	Assessment and Feedback	3.50	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.36	Moderately Extensive

The extent of pedagogical delivery priorities represents the emphasis on various instructional methods and approaches within education. Educational philosophies, curriculum standards, and the evolving teaching and learning landscape influence pedagogical delivery priorities. The extent to which a particular approach is prioritized may vary based on educational contexts, institutional goals, and the needs of diverse student populations. Traditional lecture-based teaching, collaborative learning, project-based methods, and technology integration are pedagogical approaches that educators may prioritize to varying degrees (Francisti et.al., 2023).

The evolving nature of education, influenced by technological advancements and educational research, also contributes to the dynamic nature of pedagogical priorities. Striking a balance between proven traditional methods and innovative, student-centered approaches is often essential to catering to diverse learning styles and fostering a rich educational experience. The extent of pedagogical delivery priorities reflects the values and goals set by educational institutions, with a constant emphasis on creating effective and engaging learning environments for students (Atteberry LaCour, 2021).

Significant Relationship Between Non-Teaching Responsibilities and Pedagogical Delivery Priorities

Table 2 flaunts the yielded results of the significant relationship between non-teaching responsibilities and pedagogical delivery priorities. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant

correlation between non-teaching responsibilities and pedagogical delivery priorities must be rejected, for it provides empirical evidence of significant results. It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant strong positive correlation between non-teaching responsibilities ($r=0.859$; $p<.000$) and pedagogical delivery priorities.

Table 2. Significant Relationship between Doing Non-Teaching Responsibilities and Pedagogical Delivery Priorities

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Non-teaching responsibilities Pedagogical delivery priorities	0.859	<0.000	Significant	Reject H_0

Estaji and Dezfoolian (2018) sought to investigate the significant relationship between engaging in non-teaching responsibilities and ped-

agogical delivery priorities, underscoring educators’ multifaceted role in the educational landscape. Teachers often find themselves involved

in non-teaching duties such as administrative tasks, extracurricular activities, and committee participation, impacting the time and energy they allocate to pedagogical delivery. The balance between these responsibilities influences the priorities set for instructional methods and approaches in the classroom. When teachers are burdened with excessive non-teaching tasks, it may compromise the time and focus available for developing and implementing innovative pedagogical strategies. Conversely, effectively integrating non-teaching responsibilities into the educational framework can enrich the learn-

Domains of Non-Teaching Responsibilities Significantly Influence Pedagogical Delivery Priorities

Table 3 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the indicators of doing non-teaching responsibilities significantly influence pedagogical delivery priorities. Domains of non-teaching responsibilities, such as administrative duties (0.000), professional development (0.001), student support service (0.000), parent and community engagement (0.000), and school committee participation (0.001), suggest significant influence over pedagogical delivery priorities. Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.878

In the context of teachers, role strain theory can be applied to understand how educators manage the complex interplay between their teaching roles and non-teaching responsibilities, such as administrative duties, student support, or committee participation (Siegemund, 2021). This theory sheds light on the potential stressors and conflicts that can arise when juggling diverse roles. It highlights the importance of support mechanisms, time management, and coping strategies to mitigate the negative impacts of role strain and maintain overall well-being and effectiveness in each role. Role strain theory provides valuable insights into the com-

ing experience. For instance, involvement in extracurricular activities might complement pedagogical priorities by providing students with holistic development opportunities. Therefore, the relationship between non-teaching responsibilities and pedagogical delivery priorities is dynamic, requiring a thoughtful and balanced approach to ensure that educators can effectively prioritize and execute innovative and student-centered teaching methods while fulfilling other essential roles within the school community (Tohochynskyi et al., 2021).

suggests that 87.8% of the variance in pedagogical delivery priorities is explained by non-teaching responsibilities. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (264.857) and F-statistic are significant $p < .001$, which indicates that the model better predicts exceptional education outcomes. The result I applied through the Role Strain Theory, rooted in sociology, explores the challenges and conflicts individuals experience while simultaneously fulfilling multiple roles and responsibilities. It posits that individuals, such as teachers, often hold various roles in their lives, and these roles can exert demands and pressures that may lead to strain.

plexities of educators' professional lives and the challenges they face in balancing their diverse responsibilities within educational settings (Vogel et.al, 2018). Dewi et.al. (2020) determine that the relationship between the domains of non-teaching responsibilities substantially influences the priorities set for pedagogical delivery within the educational landscape. When educators are tasked with administrative duties, committee participation, or extracurricular responsibilities, the allocation of time and energy to pedagogical priorities may shift. For example, Estaji and Dezfoolian (2018) sought to investigate how heavy administrative loads might limit

Table 3. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Non-Teaching Responsibilities Significantly Influencing Pedagogical Delivery Priorities

Model	Variables	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions
H	(Intercept)	4.145	0.079	60.416	0.001	4.145
H	(Intercept)	0.313	0.175	1.066	0.270	0.204
	Administrative duties	0.227	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.324
*Reject H_0	Professional Development	0.211	0.108	0.136	1.299	0.112
*Reject H_0	Student Support Services	0.222	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.033
*Reject H_0	Parent and Community Engagement	0.242	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.035
*Reject H_0	School Committee Participation	0.257	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.312
*Reject H_0						
	R²	= 0.878				
	F-value	= 264.857				
	p-value	= ;0.001				

the time available for lesson planning and implementing innovative teaching methods. On the other hand, active involvement in extracurricular activities can offer unique opportunities to integrate practical and experiential learning into the curriculum. The extent and nature of non-teaching responsibilities can shape the teacher’s approach to instructional strategies, determining the emphasis placed on student engagement, collaborative learning, or technology integration (Li et.al., 2022). The balance between non-teaching duties and pedagogical priorities is piv-

otal, as an optimal integration can enhance the overall educational experience. Schools and educational institutions need to recognize this relationship and provide adequate support and resources to ensure that educators can fulfill non-teaching responsibilities without compromising the quality and innovation of pedagogical delivery (Atteberry et al., 2021). The synergy between these domains is crucial for creating a conducive environment that fosters effective and dynamic teaching methods (Li Li, 2022).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

In this chapter, the outcomes, conclusions, and recommendations are delineated by the analyzed and discussed data, along with the implications drawn from the findings. The findings emanate from the articulated problem statement, while the conclusions are derived from the results. The recommendations, in turn, are formulated based on the implications gleaned from the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are the study’s findings, which are given in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of non-teaching responsibilities in terms

of administrative duties and school committee participation is often manifested, while student support services and professional development are sometimes manifested, and parent and com-

munity engagement is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating denotes that the extent of implementation of the disciplinary challenges index is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of non-teaching responsibilities regarding the use of technology, assessment and feedback, and differentiation is often manifested, while learning objectives are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating denotes that the extent of implementation of the disciplinary challenges index is sometimes manifested, thus moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between non-teaching responsibilities and pedagogical delivery priorities. Domains of non-teaching responsibilities, such as administrative duties, professional development, student support service, parent and community engagement, and school committee participation, suggest significant influence over pedagogical delivery priorities.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions: The extent of non-teaching responsibilities in terms of administrative duties and school committee participation is often manifested, while student support services and professional development are sometimes manifested, and parent and community engagement is rarely manifested. This denotes that the extent of implementation of the disciplinary challenges index is sometimes manifested, thus moderately extensive. The extent of non-teaching responsibilities regarding the use of technology, assessment and feedback, and differentiation is often manifested, while learning objectives are sometimes manifested. This denotes that the extent of implementation of the disciplinary challenges index is sometimes manifested, thus moderately extensive. There is a significant correlation between non-teaching responsibilities and pedagogical delivery priorities. Domains of non-teaching responsibilities in administrative duties, professional development, student

support service, parent and community engagement, and school committee participation suggest significant influence over pedagogical delivery priorities. Role Strain Theory explores the challenges and conflicts individuals experience when simultaneously fulfilling multiple roles and responsibilities. It posits that individuals, such as teachers, often hold various roles in their lives, and these roles can exert demands and pressures that may lead to strain. In the context of teachers, role strain theory can be applied to understand how educators manage the complex interplay between their teaching roles and non-teaching responsibilities, such as administrative duties, student support, or committee participation. This theory sheds light on the potential stressors and conflicts that can arise when juggling diverse roles. It highlights the importance of support mechanisms, time management, and coping strategies to mitigate the negative impacts of role strain and maintain overall well-being and effectiveness in each role. Role strain theory provides valuable insights into the complexities of educators' professional lives and the challenges they face in balancing their diverse responsibilities within educational settings.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. The supervisor may conduct a comprehensive review of the workload distribution among teachers, ensuring a fair balance between teaching and non-teaching responsibilities. The supervisor should implement policies that promote efficient delegation of non-teaching tasks, allowing educators to prioritize pedagogical delivery without undue strain. Additionally, providing professional development opportunities focused on time management and workload optimization would further support teachers in achieving a healthy equilibrium. School Principal. The study suggests implementing a transparent system for assigning and

monitoring non-teaching responsibilities. Principals should actively seek teacher input in determining workload distribution and fostering a collaborative and supportive work environment. Creating a culture that values and acknowledges the efforts of teachers in both teaching and non-teaching domains contributes to a positive school climate. Furthermore, the principal is encouraged to explore innovative approaches to streamline administrative processes, thus minimizing the impact of non-teaching duties on pedagogical priorities. Teacher. The study recommends proactive communication with school administration to express concerns related to workload balance. Teachers are encouraged to collaborate with colleagues to share strategies for effectively managing both teaching and non-teaching responsibilities. Additionally, participating in professional development opportunities focused on time management and work-life balance is advised to enhance coping mechanisms and resilience. Future Researcher. The study suggests delving deeper into the systemic factors affecting the balance between teaching and non-teaching responsibilities and its impact on pedagogical priorities. Exploring diverse educational contexts, considering regional variations, and investigating the long-term effects of workload distribution on teacher retention and job satisfaction would contribute to a more comprehensive understanding. Future researchers are encouraged to employ quantitative and qualitative methodologies to capture the nuances of this complex relationship and provide actionable insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers.

5. References

5. References

- Administration for Children & Families (2018). Parent, Family, and Community Engagement Framework for Early Childhood Systems*
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Parent+and+Community+Engagement+as+component+of+non-teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&id=ED609027>
- AITF For the Management of Infectious Diseases
<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/downloads/2021/05may/20210520-IATF->
- Ajloni, M. S.; O'Toole, John Mitchell (2021). The Influence of Teacher Educational and Technological Factors on Video-Based Pedagogical Responses in Jordan: An Integrative Mixed Methods Study *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, v5 n1 p65-87 2021
- Akhigbe, J. Nosakhare; Adeyemi, Adeola Eunice (2020). Using Gender Responsive Collaborative Learning Strategy to Improve Students' Achievement and Attitude towards Learning Science in Virtual and Hands-On Laboratory Environment *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, v4 n3 p241-261 2020
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=pedagogical+delivery+&ft=on&id=EJ1280913>
- Andrews, Carolyn Bancroft; Motz, Benjamin A.; Israel, Jamie G.; Leary, Heather (2020). Characteristics of Students Who Opted in to Use the Boost Mobile App as an Educational Support Service *Journal of Teaching and Learning with Technology*, v9 p158-170 2020
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Student+support+services+as+component+of+non-teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&pg=2&id=EJ1290316>
- Atteberry, Allison; LaCour, Sarah E. (2021). Making a Tough Choice: Teacher Target-Setting and Student Achievement in a Teacher Performance System Using Student Learning Objectives *AERA Open*, v7 n1 Jan-Dec 2021
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Learning+objectives+of+teachers&ft=on&id=EJ1323728>
- Awang, Yunita; Mohamed, Norazamina; Ahmad, Suraya; Nasir, Noor Emilina Mohd (2021). Examining the Influence of Academic and Non-Academic Responsibilities on Academicians' Job-Related Stress in Higher Education *Asian Journal of University Education*, v17 n4 p498-510 Oct 2021
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Administrative+responsibilities+as+component+of+non-teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&id=EJ1328507>
- Balyer, Aydin; Özcan, Kenan (2020). Teachers' Perceptions of Their Awareness of Social Roles and Efforts to Perform These Roles *South African Journal of Education*, v40 n2 Article 1723 May 2020

- Baydar, Fatih (2022). The Relationship between Participation in Administrative Decisions and School Effectiveness: An Empirical Study on Teachers *International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies*, v9 n1 p143-152 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=school+committee+participation++of+teachers&ft=on&id=EJ1332281>
- Buchanan, R. (2020). An Ecological Framework for Supervision in Teacher Education *Journal of Educational Supervision*, v3 n1 Article 6 p76-94 2020 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=teacher%27s+Ecological+Systems+Theory&ft=on&id=EJ1250285>
- Cancino, Marco; Ibarra, Paloma (2023). EFL Secondary Education Teachers' Perceptions toward Using Online Student Response Systems *PROFILE: Issues in Teachers' Professional Development*, v25 n1 p97-111 Jan-Jun 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=assessment+and+feedback++as+component+of+pedagogical+priority&ft=on&id=EJ1368190>
- Carvalho, Marisa; Cabral, Ilidia; Verdasca, José; Alves, José (2021). What about Us? Teachers' Participation in Schools' Strategic Action Plans *Participatory Educational Research*, v8 n3 p156-175 Aug 2021 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=school+committee+participation++of+teachers&ft=on&id=EJ1290596>
- Castro-Rodríguez, Elena; Ruiz-Hidalgo, Juan F.; Lupiáñez, Jose L.; Fernández-Plaza, Jose A.; Rico, Luis; Segovia, Isidoro; Flores, Pablo (2022). Specific Mathematics Learning Objectives Expressed by Teachers in Training *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, v17 n2 Article em0675 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Learning+objectives+of+teachers&ft=on&id=EJ1336145>
- Demirkol, Mehmet (2022). Stereotypes of the Teaching Profession *International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies*, v9 spec is p998-1011 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Administrative+responsibilities+as+component+of+non+teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&id=EJ1355206>
- Dewi, Mutiara Sari; Setyosari, Punaji; Kuswandi, Dedi; Ulfa, Saida (2020). Analysis of Kindergarten Teachers on Pedagogical Content Knowledge *European Journal of Educational Research*, v9 n4 p1701-1721 2020 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=dirrefentiation++as+component+of+pedagogical+priority&ft=on&id=EJ1272481>
- Ercan Demirel, Eda; Erdirençelebi, Meral (2016). The Relationship of Burnout with Workaholism Mediated by Work-Family Life Conflict: A Study on Female Academicians *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, v15 n4 p1300-1316

- Eroglu, Mehmet (2022). Investigation of Emergency Remote Education Experiences of Prospective Teachers: A Framework for Participation *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching*, v9 n4 p1852-1874 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=school+committee+participation++of+teachers&ft=on&id=EJ1353457>
- Estaji, M.; Dezfoolian, Shabnam (2018). EFL Teacher's Pedagogical Knowledge Base as a Predictor of Teacher's Reflectivity: Comparing Different Components and Perceptions *International Journal of Instruction*, v11 n3 p491-510 Jul 2018
- Fitriani, Somariah; Istaryatiningtias (2020). Promoting Child-Friendly School Model through School Committee as Parents' Participation *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, v9 n4 p1025-1034 Dec 2020 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=school+committee+participation++of+teachers&ft=on&id=EJ1274597>
- Francisti, Jan; Balogh, Zoltán; Turcáni, Milan (2023). The Use of Internet of Things Technology in the Pedagogical Process *International Baltic Symposium on Science and Technology Education*, Paper presented at the International Baltic Symposium on Science and Technology Education (BalticSTE2023) (5th, Šiauliai, Lithuania, Jun 12-15, 2023)
- Gujarati, D.N. & Porter, D.C. (2009). *Basic Econometrics*. 5th Edition, McGraw-Hill Irwin, Boston, 400.
- Hamamoto, Nobuhiko (2023). Issues in Support for Students in "School as a Team": Examination of School-Based Teams in the U.K. and Japan *Educational Studies in Japan: International Yearbook*, n17 p45-57 Mar 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Student+support+services+as+component+of+non+teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&id=EJ1382351>
- Hanny, C. N.; Graham, Charles R.; West, Richard E.; Borup, Jered (2023). "Someone in Their Corner": Parental Support in Online Secondary Education *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, v24 n1 p85-105 Feb 2023
- Hayes, L.; Lachlan-Haché, Lisa; Williams, Haidee (2022). 10 Mentoring and Induction Challenges in Rural Schools and How to Address Them *Center on Great Teachers and Leaders* <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=non+teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&id=ED602971>
- Hine, Megumi G. (2022). Words Matter: Differences in Informative and Negative

- School Communication in Engaging Families *School Community Journal*, v32 n1 p157-186 2022
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Parent+and+Community+Engagement+as+component+of+non+teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&id=EJ1347510>
- Hume, S.; Griffin, Tabatha; Andrahannadi, Upekha (2022). Effective Teaching Practices and Student Support Services in Online VET. Research Report *National Centre for Vocational Education Research (NCVER)*
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Student+support+services+as+component+of+non+teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&id=ED628926>
- Kim, Jung-Hyun; Koo, Soo-Hyun (2022). It Was Teacher Identities, Learning and Teaching Experience That Affected Teaching Practices *MEXTESOL Journal*, v46 n1 2022
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Administrative+responsibilities+as+component+of+non+teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&id=EJ1333910>
- Konstantinou, Charalambos I.; Konstantinou, Ioannis Ch. (2021). Determinants of Teacher Effectiveness: Pedagogical and Didactic Training *Open Journal for Educational Research*, v5 n1 p11-24 2021
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Pedagogical+Priorities+of+teachers&ft=on&id=EJ1306785>
- Li, Yuheng; Rakovic, Mladen; Poh, Boon Xin; Gašević, Dragan; Chen, Guanliang (2022). Automatic Classification of Learning Objectives Based on Bloom's Taxonomy *International Educational Data Mining Society*, Paper presented at the International Conference on Educational Data Mining (EDM) (15th, Durham, United Kingdom, Jul 24-27, 2022)
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Learning+objectives+of+teachers&ft=on&id=ED624058>
- Li, Bing; Li, Zheng (2022). Capturing School Context Characteristics Using the Job Demands-Resources Model: Adaptation and Validation *International Journal of Educational Methodology*, v8 n4 p647-654 2022
[https://eric.ed.gov/?q=teacher%27s+Job+Demands-Resources+\(JD-R\)+Model+&ft=on&id=EJ1368556](https://eric.ed.gov/?q=teacher%27s+Job+Demands-Resources+(JD-R)+Model+&ft=on&id=EJ1368556)
- Lim, L. (2019). Work Intensification and the Secondary Vice-Principal Role *Canadian Journal of Educational Administration and Policy*, n190 p64-72 2019
<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=wide+range+of+tasks%2c+duties%2c+and+roles+that+educators&ft=on&id=EJ1223829>
- Mayger, L. K.; Provenzano, Kathleen (2022). Searching for Equity-Centered Change Agents: An Investigation of Family and Community Engagement in Teacher Evaluation Frameworks *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, v30 n1 Jan 2022

- Mariscal, Liza L.; Albarracin, Melanie R.; Mobo, Froilan D.; Cutillas, Anesito L. (2023). Pedagogical Competence towards Technology-Driven Instruction on Basic Education *Online Submission*, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research* v4 n5 p1567-1580 May 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=use+of+technology++as+component+of+pedagogical+priority&ft=on&id=ED628659>
- Mohammadi, Mojtaba; Zarrabi, Maryam; Kamali, Jaber (2023). Formative Assessment Feedback to Enhance the Writing Performance of Iranian IELTS Candidates: Blending Teacher and Automated Writing Evaluation *International Journal of Language Testing*, v13 n1 p206-224 Mar 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=assessment+and+feedback++as+component+of+pedagogical+priority&ft=on&id=EJ1385139>
- Nagashima, Tomohiro; Yang, Kexin; Bartel, Anna N.; Silla, Elena M.; Vest, Nicholas A.; Alibali, Martha W.; Alevin, Vincent (2020). Pedagogical Affordance Analysis: Leveraging Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge to Elicit Pedagogical Affordances and Constraints of Instructional Tools *Grantee Submission*, Paper presented at the Annual Meeting of ISLS (2020) <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Pedagogical+Priorities+of+teachers&ft=on&id=ED623512>
- Nash, B. L. (2022). "We Felt Like Pioneers": Exploring the Social and Emotional Dimensions of Teachers' Learning during Online Professional Development *Journal of Online Learning Research*, v8 n1 p101-125 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Professional+Development+as+component+of+non+teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&pg=2&id=EJ1342759>
- Nguyen, Dinh Thien Bao (2022). The Role of CALL in the Ecology of Language Teachers' Well-Being and Professional Development *Research-publishing.net*, Paper presented at the EUROCALL 2022 Conference (30th, Reykjavik, Iceland, Aug 17-19, 2022) <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=teacher%27s+Ecological+Systems+Theory&ft=on&id=ED625203>.
- Ozdemir, Tuncay Yavuz; Cakalci, Neslihan (2022). How School Climate Affects Teachers' Individual Innovativeness: The Mediating Role of Teacher Autonomy *Educational Process: International Journal*, v11 n4 p69-91 2022
- Pallant, J. (2020). *SPSS Survival Manual: A step-by-step guide to data analysis using IBM SPSS (7th ed.)*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003117452>

- Salikhova, N. R.; Lynch, Martin F.; Salikhova, Albina B. (2020). Psychological Aspects of Digital Learning: A Self-Determination Theory Perspective *Contemporary Educational Technology*, v12 n2 Article ep280 2020 [https://eric.ed.gov/?q=teacher%27s+Self-Determination+Theory+\(SDT\)+&ft=on&id=EJ1274310](https://eric.ed.gov/?q=teacher%27s+Self-Determination+Theory+(SDT)+&ft=on&id=EJ1274310)
- Seneviratne, Kumudu; Hamid, Junainah Abd; Khatibi, Ali; Azam, Ferdous; Sudasinghe, Sepali (2019). Teachers' Sense of Efficacy: A Challenge for Professional Development toward Teaching Science as Inquiry *Science Education International*, v30 n4 p274-283 2019 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Professional+Development+as+component+of+non+teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&pg=2&id=EJ1236350>
- Siegemund, Steffen; Johannsen, Svenja (2021). Finding a Role in Class: A Mixed Methods Study of Prospective Teachers' Beliefs Towards Co-Teaching in Inclusive Classes *International Journal of Whole Schooling*, v17 n2 p38-72 2021 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=teacher%27s+role+strain+theory+&ft=on&id=EJ1339887>
- Thant Sin, Khin Khin (2023). Teacher Learning and Professional Development in School-University Partnership: How Do Mentors Learn? *Hungarian Educational Research Journal*, v13 n1 p121-141 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Professional+Development+as+component+of+non+teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&id=EJ1385247>
- Tohochynskiy, Olekcii; Yermak, Serhii; Popryzhna, Alla; Tvrdon, Miroslav; Oleksiuk, Nataliya (2021). Professionally Oriented Training of Specialists to Work in the Conditions of the Inclusive Educational Environment *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences*, v16 n3 p1244-1254 2021 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=dirrefentiation++as+component+of+pedagogical+priority&ft=on&id=EJ1309537>
- Vogel, L. R.; Alhudithi, Ahlam (2018). Being a Saudi and Qatari Female Principal: Position Demands, Challenges, and Advice *European Journal of Educational Management*, v2 n1 p13-33 2018 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=responsibility+theory+&ft=on&id=EJ1284863>
- Weimer, Kristina R. (2021). An Intrinsic Case Study of One Music Educator's Professional Development through Podcasting *Contributions to Music Education*, v46 p245-263 2021 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Professional+Development+as+component+of+non+teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&id=EJ1305287>

- Williams-McBean, C. T. (2022). Assessment Tools and Strategies Used by Jamaican Secondary School Teachers *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education*, v9 n4 p883-905 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=dirrefentiation++as+used+by+teachers+&ft=on&id=EJ1378752>
- Wilson, Marguerite Anne Fillion; Robinson-Perez, Ada; Yull, Denise Gray (2021). From School Exclusion to Provisional Access: Possibilities and Limitations of a Critical Class-Conscious Parent Engagement Program in Rural Upstate New York *School Community Journal*, v31 n2 p293-323 2021 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Parent+and+Community+Engagement+as+component+of+non+teaching+responsibilities&ft=on&pg=2&id=EJ1323068>
- Yüregilli Göksu, Derya; Duran, Volkan (2022). Investigation of Pedagogical Belief Systems and Teacher Efficacy of Teachers in Turkey *International Journal of Progressive Education*, v18 n1 p475-496 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Pedagogical+Priorities+of+teachers&ft=on&id=EJ1332679>